

HUMSS AS THE CHOSEN STRAND AND ITS INFLUENCE ON THE STUDENTS' COMMUNICATION SKILLS

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ABSTRACT

The importance of communication skills cannot be disregarded, especially today where communication plays a crucial part in our daily lives. Furthermore, poor communication skills may lead to the inability to maintain professional and personal relationships. With this study aims to investigate and determine whether there is a statistically significant correlation between students majoring in the humanities and social sciences and their level of proficiency in social academic communication skills. This correlational study is delimited to thirty (30) students under Humanities and Social Sciences strand at a higher educational institution residing at the City of San Fernando, Pampanga, Philippines. The researchers of this study have utilized random sampling technique in selecting the respondents. The data of the assessment and survey questionnaires gathered from the respondents were evaluated using descriptive statistics. It is revealed through this study that there is a positive inclination among students for active participation in various group discussions, emphasizing the significance of collaborative learning experiences. Students perceive the connection between communication skills and success within their respective academic strands, indicating the perceived impact of effective communication on academic achievement. Additionally, it is recommended for some humanities and social sciences students to consider interpersonal interaction. This recommendation may lead to the improvement of knowledge, attending extracurricular performances, understanding textbooks, and using qualitative techniques such as interviewing to understand students' experiences and barriers to communication.

Keywords: *Communication, Senior High School, Communication Skills, Socio-Academic Skills*

INTRODUCTION

Communication is defined as the delivery, receipt, or exchange of information, thoughts, or ideas so that everyone involved completely comprehends the message. Communication is a two-way process that comprises the sender, message, channel, receiver, feedback, and context. Communication skills relate to a person's ability to successfully express information, thoughts, ideas, and feelings to others. These talents span a wide range of communication modalities, including verbal and nonverbal communication, writing communication, and listening. Effective communication skills include the ability to express oneself effectively, grasp what others are saying, and engage in meaningful and fruitful interactions. Good communication skills may help you go through life more effortlessly, making it simpler to connect with others. Poor communication skills, on the other hand, can damage professional and personal relationships.

On the other hand, skills in communication refer to how well students can execute these procedures effectively. As a result, the efficacy of communication plays a crucial part in making a choice, specifically whether there are advantages or disadvantages in the communication process (Hermawan et al. 2022). Meanwhile, communication skills inculcate professionalism in speaking styles, modes of self-expression, and attitudes toward others (Lucanus, 2015), and these attributes will serve students well in their professional careers. Communication skills are defined as the capacity to offer and receive various types of information, as well as to develop one's personality throughout one's life. (Abdikarimova et al., 2021). Daily, students engage in large numbers, exchanging news, ideas, sentiments, knowledge, and different points of view. Nowadays, studies show that this capacity is the most important aspect of higher education in terms of considering and maintaining positive connections with other individuals consequently, all students require these abilities to avoid miscommunication and difficulties.

Conversely, written communication is a subset of nonverbal communication that focuses on exchanging ideas through written language. It is employed to creatively or academically express ideas and opinions. When it comes to written communication, slow learners' abilities are categorized as non-fluent because some students struggle with writing correctly, while others simply do not want to write (Nanang et al. 2016). They are employed in writing to transmit messages. Many students struggle to communicate ideas or express themselves in writing because some are better at it orally than in writing, and some find it difficult to do both. While everyone agrees that having strong oral and writing communication skills is essential, there is substantial (Raba, 2017). Speaking capabilities are just as important as other skills that must be acquired to increase communication among the intended language learners. In the language school environment, speaking is a process in which students use discourse to negotiate meaning and put their newly gained language abilities to use.

Social Academic Communication Skills

A person's capacity to connect, cooperate, and communicate well in an academic or educational context is referred to as their social academic communication abilities. By improving their communication abilities, students may deepen their bonds with themselves, others, and society. Communication skills are also necessary for the development of abilities and sensitivity in people's social lives, as well as the construction of constructive interpersonal relationships and the eradication of cultural barriers (Rubtsova, 2019). Because they enable students to articulate their learning outcomes and achieve successful learning outcomes, communication skills are vital to academic success (Supena et al., 2021).

Social and academic communication skills demonstrate that there are several factors to good communication in educational contexts. Collaboration, cultural knowledge, digital literacy, clear written and verbal contact, active listening, and critical thinking are all part of the process. To foster a positive learning environment and encourage academic success, it is crucial for learners, teachers, and institutions to acquire and refine these abilities. In order to feel confident and motivated for academic pursuits, learners desire to be able to communicate effectively with their peers and instructors at educational institutions (Alawamleh et al., 2020). Effective communication skills are critical for teachers in conveying instruction, classroom management, and interaction with students in the classroom. The teacher must instruct kids with varied ways of thinking.

Impact of communication skills among HUMSS students

Addressing the relationship between these interpersonal abilities and career preparation can benefit students as well as educators by allowing for the adaptation of learning methodologies and individuals' success in a variety of professional settings. This study recognizes the importance of these skills in deciding students' potential career paths and seeks to shed some insight into the relationship between communication competency and career preparation among students majoring in the humanities and social sciences. It is widely known that effective communication skills are required for success in both academic and professional settings. Students specializing in humanities and social sciences are known in academic circles for honing their analytical, communication, and critical thinking skills. These skills include empathy, critical thinking, and the capacity to have meaningful conversations about challenging social and personal issues. Inadequate verbal communication and teamwork are two examples of poor communication at work. Errors in communication, unreliability, and malevolent communication could also be factors in their coworkers (Puscas et al. 2021).

Work immersion programs should help students prepare for these potential obstacles by offering the required direction, support, and training. It may involve instruction on workplace customs and guidelines, teamwork and communication techniques, time management strategies, and mentorship and supervision from upper management as explained by seasoned experts (Kurtz et al. 2017). Not only are effective

communication skills essential in the job, but they also demonstrate a well-rounded education. Because their coursework covers a wide range of topics, students majoring in the humanities and social sciences develop great interpersonal skills that extend beyond academic debate. According to Fahmi and Ali (2022), time-related factors, the key elements impacting students' dropouts from MOOC courses were discovered to be motivation, interaction, subject matter, workload, and communication. Additionally, Gaur (2020), discovered that interpersonal variables such as institution and familial assistance, interaction, and communication (social presence) can be utilized to anticipate a high risk of dropout among learners in virtual settings.

Humanities and Social Sciences Academic Course

An academic course in the humanities and social sciences that focuses on communication is an extensive area of study that looks at the craft of effective communication to investigate the complexities of society dynamics and human experience. This course explores the various facets of people exchanging ideas, information, and stories in private and public settings. According to Sudi et al. (2024) asserts that studying the humanities fosters students' ability to 5 communicate effectively, broadens their perspective on the world, and fosters the growth of their capacity for critical and creative thought. According to Evans et al. (2024), it supports educators and students in creating well-rounded thinkers by highlighting cultural and ethical commitments and values. regarding the essential communication skills covered in the HUMSS strand.

Oral communication abilities are necessary for thinking and learning, and they are crucial for the development of literacy. It serves as the binding agent between all the constituent parts of a language. Talk helps students organize their experience and knowledge, explore, and comprehend ideas and concepts, identify, and solve problems, and express and clarify their thoughts, feelings, and opinions in addition to helping them communicate information¹. It covers a broad range of topics, such as language, media studies, interpersonal relationships, and communication theory, giving students the tools they need to understand and improve their communication abilities. Essentially, this course provides a comprehensive method for deciphering the nuances of interpersonal communication, empowering students to thrive in a globalized society where proficient communication is an essential ability. While social sciences are an academic field that focuses on how people interact in society, institutions, and the wider world, humanities study will help you develop your writing, information analysis, and research skills as well as your critical and creative thinking abilities.

Research Questions

The purpose of this correlational study is to investigate and determine whether there is a statistically significant correlation between students majoring in Humanities and Social Sciences and their level of proficiency in social academic communication skills. This research specifically aims to respond to the following questions:

1. What is the participation rate of students in participating in various group discussions, and team projects in terms of school-related work?
2. What are the communication breakdowns faced by the Humanities and Social Sciences Students?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the student's chosen academic strand and their communication skills?

METHODOLOGY

The study utilized a non-experimental method that was quantitative, namely a descriptive correlational analysis. Quantitative research is used to test hypotheses by examining the relationship between variables. It utilizes statistical and numerical methodologies. According to Creswell (2014), quantitative research is an inquiry into a social or human problem based on testing a theory composed of variables, measured with numbers, and analyzed with statistical procedures to determine whether the predictive generalizations of the theory hold true. Additionally, a correlational study is utilized wherein this approach to research does not attempt to manipulate the variables; it describes the relationship between two variables within a single group. In the lens of Tan (2014), correlational research aims to establish correlations between two or more variables. Simply expressed, it examines to see if a rise or decrease in one variable corresponds to an increase or decrease in another. In terms of the respondents of this study. The researchers focused on 30 students hailing from the Grades 11 and 12 of the Humanities and Social Sciences strand at a higher educational institution situated City of San Fernando, Pampanga, Philippines using the non-probability sampling specifically the random sampling technique. Considering Stratton (2021), a simple random sample technique is a population subset that has been chosen randomly. In this sampling procedure, each member of the population has an exactly equal probability of being selected.

In collecting data from the respondents, the researchers utilized a researcher-made questionnaire in accordance with the study's objective. The survey questionnaire was distributed to participants using various forms of media, notably Google Forms. In collecting the data, the researchers of this study have followed the ethics in research by ensuring that the respondents are wary of the pivotal role they will play on the study as well as treating the data with full anonymity and confidentiality in accordance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012. To evaluate the relationship between Humanities and Social Sciences students and their social academic communication skills the researcher organized and evaluated the data using Pearson r Correlation Coefficient to identify the strength as well as the course of a linear correlation that exists between two independent variables, in this case, academic majors (Humanities and Social Sciences) and Social academic communication skills. In this context, a positive relationship would indicate that as students prefer the Humanities major, their social academic communication skills are enhanced whereas an opposite relationship would indicate that as students move

through the Social Sciences major, their communication skills could become less effective.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Sex

The frequency and percentage of the respondents in our study based on their sex are shown in Table 1. Based on the data collected through the survey questionnaires handed out to the respondents, female respondents obtained a frequency of 18 (60%), making it the highest respondents between the two. On the other hand, male respondents have a total of 12 (40%). With that, it is implied that most of the respondents who answered our survey are female.

Age

The frequency distribution and the percentage of the respondents according to their age are shown in table 1. The results show that most of the respondents are 17 years old with a frequency of 16 (53.3%). Whereas 15-year-old respondents garnered the lowest frequency of 1 (3.3%). On the other hand, 16-year-old respondents got a frequency of 8 (26.7%). Second to the last 18-year-old respondents got a frequency of 3(10%). Lastly 19-year-old respondents obtained second to lowest of frequency 2 (6.7%). This data offers the indication of the frequency distribution and percentage of the respondents according to their age group.

Grade and Section

The frequency distribution and respective percentages of the respondents according to their Grade and Section are shown in Table 1. Based on the data that was collected, it appears that most of the respondents that answered our survey are from Grade 12-Y1-2R with a total of 10 (33.3%). The lowest respondents shown in the results are from the Grade 11-Y1-1P with a frequency of zero. Second to the lowest respondents are from the Grade 12-Y1-1P garnered a frequency of 2 (6.7%). Next are from the Grade 11-Y1-1R and Grade 11-Y1-2R obtaining both a frequency of 4 (13.3%). Lastly, are from the Grade 11-Y1-3R and Grade 12-Y1-1R both having a frequency of 5 (16.7%).

Table 1
Frequency Distribution and Percentage of the Respondents table

<i>Demographic profile</i>		Frequency	%
Sex	Male	12	40.0
	Female	18	60.0
Age	15 yrs. old	1	3.3
	889		

	16 yrs. old	8	26.7
	17 yrs. old	16	53.3
	18 yrs. old	3	10
	19 yrs. old	2	6.7
Grade 11			
	1P	0	0
	1R	4	13.3
	2R	4	13.3
	3R	5	16.7
Grade 12			
	1P	2	6.7
	1R	5	16.7
	2R	10	33.3

The participation rate of students in various discussions

As shown in Table 2, the subscale "*The participation rate of students*" has a weighted mean of 2.37 and a standard deviation of 0.85. Table 2 illustrates that most of the students "*Agreed*" that majority of them participated in various group discussions. According to Bryant et al. (2021), students who decline to take part in the mentioned activities are passive students. Participation is counted as being alert to events, answering the questions, and engaging in group discussion. As per Li et al. (2020), participation spurs students' collaboration, social interaction, the inspiration for teamwork, and the amelioration of individual improvement in the classroom. . Indeed, classroom participation plays a considerable role in improving the teaching and learning process.

Communication breakdown faced by students.

Table 2 delineated the mean and standard deviation of items under the subscale "*Communication breakdown faced by students*". This subscale has a weighted mean of 3.10 and a standard deviation of 0.15; majority of respondents "*Agreed*" on the said subscale. Communication breakdown frequently occurs in which individuals communicate with one another. As in communication, people can deliver and receive the idea or message and even negotiate the meaning (Liu et al., 2022). To establish excellent communication, the messages sent by the speaker must be comprehended by the interlocutor. The capacity to talk is critical in communication. Furthermore, communication suffers a significant breakdown in the lack of proper grammar usage. As stated by Trenholm (2020), the framework of communication strategies is a procedure that manages creating interlanguage mistakes. Communication techniques assist students in communicating with native speakers of the target language. These tactics are tools that help learners communicate effectively in the target language with native speakers. They provide a framework for navigating and managing possible communication failures, ultimately improving overall communication.

The relationship communication skills and chosen academic strand.

As Table 2 exhibited the weighted mean and a standard deviation of the subscale "*The relationship of Communication skill and academic strand*", having a weighted mean of 3.25 and standard deviation of 0.20, which means that respondents "*Agreed*" with all the items on the said subscale. Meanwhile, Communication skill is the most basic condition for the education to be done in a healthy way. There are several allusions to communication and communication skills in the most current social studies curriculum (Uygun, 2018). Having an ideal strand provides learners with a feeling of self-assurance and can assist pupils in becoming passionate about their chosen job. Humanities and Social Sciences, which focuses on acquiring a greater grasp of the arts, culture, literature, politics, and society (Magnaye, 2020).

Table 2
Descriptive Statistics for Communication Skills

Benchmark Statements for Communication Skills	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
The Participation rate of students.			
1. How confident are you that you can interact effectively with your professors and peers in a classroom situation?	2.50	0.77	Disagree
2. How often do you participate in group discussions or team projects as a requirement for your coursework?	2.96	0.80	Agree
3. Do you often participate in recitations in class?	3.30	0.66	Strongly Agree
4. How comfortable are you with giving presentations or speaking in front of your classmates and professors?	2.86	0.73	Agree
5. Do you collaborate properly with your group mates?	1.70	0.50	Strongly Disagree
6. Are you active in group discussion in class?	1.13	0.34	Strongly Disagree
7. I constantly seek opportunities for academic interaction and teamwork.	1.36	0.49	Strongly Disagree
8. With professors or instructors, I feel confident establishing a conversation with them.	3.20	0.55	Agree
Weighted Mean	2.37	0.85	Agree
Communication breakdowns faced by Students			
1. Do you believe that there is such a communication breakdown faced by the students in Humanities and Social Sciences Students?	3.26	0.52	Strongly Agree
2. Do you experience any problems with comprehension of complicated educational content and clearly expressing ideas?	2.93	0.69	Agree
3. Do you feel any communication breakdowns during public speaking?	3.03	0.71	Agree
4. Reviews from other people offer valuable insights about my interpersonal strengths and weaknesses.	3.2	0.55	Agree
Weighted Mean	3.10	0.15	Agree

The relationship of communication skills and chosen academic strand

1.Do you feel that your academic program (Humanities or Social Sciences) has helped you improve your communication skills?	3.3	0.66	Agree
2.Do you consider having strong interpersonal communication skills have an impact in the academic state of Humanities and Social Sciences students?	3.43	0.56	Strongly Agree
3.There has been noticeable progress in my communication skills since starting my academic program.	3.4	0.49	Strongly Agree
4.Do you agree that humanities and social science contributes to make your communication skills efficient?	3.4	0.62	Strongly Agree
5.In academic presentations, I have no issues expressing my thoughts and opinions.	2.96	0.76	Agree
6. I consider myself integrated socially in my academic program.	3.03	0.66	Agree
Weighted Mean	3.25	0.20	Agree
Grand Weighted Mean	2.90	0.60	Agree

Relationship between Communication Skills and Academic Strand of the Respondents

Pearson r is utilized to assess the relationship between communication skills and academic strand of the respondents. The result shows a not significant positive relationship between the communication skills and academic strand of the respondents. ($r = 0.177$, $p = 0.566$). As can be understood from the definitions, communication is the necessity of people living together and becoming social beings. The adequacy of the relationship between individuals as well as quality and power are related to the proper and effective establishment of communication. Because the more beneficial and more understandable the conversation, the more success, economic and social development, and personal integrity develop (Karacan and Akoglu, 2021). Meanwhile, Mascuñana and Lazaro (2022) mentioned that the relationship between the two variables is only significant on an average level. As a result, the efficiency of language activities is judged not merely by their strand specialization or whether they are aimed to educate students for their future careers.

Table 3

Test of Correlation between the Communication skills and Academic strand of the respondents

<i>Communication and Academic Skills</i>				
<i>Variable</i>	<i>r value</i>	<i>p value</i>	<i>Degree of Relationship</i>	<i>Level of Significance</i>
Communication Skills	0.177	0.566	Positive with Relationship	Not Significant
Academic Strand	0.177	0.566	Positive with Relationship	Not Significant

Conclusions

The following are the conclusions in accordance with the summary of the results.

1. The profiles of the respondents were classified based on their grade level, communication skills, and written skills. With regards to their grade level, there are 13 students in grade 11 (43.3%) and 17 students in grade 12 (56.7%) were classified as respondents.
2. The Knowledge of the respondents in terms of their social academic skills which is composed of 30 items. The percentage of the scores of the respondents ranges from 10- 100% with 15 out of 30 items answered agree and the remaining 15 yielded answers disagree and strongly agree the percentage of responses.
3. The correlation between the respondents and their social academic communication was delineated through the following subscales: The participation rate of students ($\bar{x} = 2.37$, $SD = 0.85$), Communication breakdowns faced by Students ($\bar{x} = 3.10$, $SD = 0.15$), The relationship communication skills and chosen academic strand ($\bar{x} = 3.25$, $SD = 0.20$).
4. The test of correlation between the respondent's demographic profile and communication was evaluated using Descriptive statistics. Results revealed based on the verbal interpretation the respondent does have a significant relationship with their communication and their academic strand.
5. The test of correlation between the respondents' communication skills and academic strand was evaluated using Pearson r. Results revealed that the respondents' communications skills does not have a significant relationship with the academic strand with a rating of ($r=0.177$, $p= 0.566$) which means there's no significant relationship between the two variables.

Recommendations

In consideration of the summary of results, findings, and conclusion, the following recommendations are suggested:

1. Given that the study's scope is limited to Humanities and Social Sciences students, it may be suggested that other learners associated with the strand should be considered because interpersonal interaction manifests itself and applied to every individual in any circumstances, at any time, and at any cost due to communication is one of our methods of conversing and conveying thoughts as well as concepts with others.
 2. The researchers urge that students improve their understanding of knowledge to have more effective exchanges of information with other individuals and prevent or minimize difficulties with communication while speaking with people or with one another.
 3. Learners in the Humanities and Social Sciences may benefit from attending more extracurricular performances that help them improve their interpersonal relationships and speaking abilities.
 4. Understanding a lot of textbooks or literary works might be suggested to improve our written communication vocabulary, grammar, and writing abilities.
 5. To understand more about the subjective experiences and perspectives of the respondents, qualitative techniques like as interviewing may be used to supplement the quantitative findings and acquire more comprehensive knowledge into the barriers to communication that students face.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research strictly adheres to the ethical standards set by the institution and the body of knowledge. All information and data coming from the respondents are solely for academic purposes only. In line also with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, the researchers strictly preserved the anonymity and confidentiality of the respondents.

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